

AGRI AND ALLIED PRODUCTS EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Agricultural sector is the backbone of country. India's major export contribution on the hands of agriculture products. Major income for India had raised from the agricultural sector. Increases in agricultural products exports leads to develop the Indian economy. Agriculture's history was showing the culture of Indians. For development of industry, agriculture plays a major role of exporting crucial goods such as Sugar, jute, vegetable oil and so on. India's agriculture GDP had increased to 19.9 percentage. Main objective of the study to find out the major export performance of the agri and allied products of India during the period of 2009-2022. This study make use of statistical calculation such as percentage analysis, growth rate analysis, standard deviation, CAGR and AAGR in analysis the data finding the result.

Key Words: Agri & Allied Products, Export Data, Trend Analysis

Introduction:

As per a report by World Trade Organization (WTO) on the trends in world agricultural trade in the past 25 years, India and Mexico with 3.1% and 3.4% share in global Agri exports, respectively, replaced New Zealand (9th) and Malaysia (7th) as the largest exporters across the globe. The United States of America (USA), which topped the list in 1995 with 22.2% share of world Agri export, was overtaken by the European Union (EU) in 2019 with 16.1% global Agri share. The USA's exports reduced to 13.8% in 2019 while Brazil maintained its ranking as the third-largest exporter by increasing its share from 4.8% in 1995 to 7.8% in 2019.

Agriculture continues to be the main stay of the District Faridkot and is known for the production of Cotton, Rice, Wheat, Pulses, Vegetables & fruit crops. Besides this, other agriculture allied activities includes area under horticulture and vegetable crops, dairy, floriculture, fishery and forestry. The important sectors consider include Agriculture, Horticulture, Animal husbandry, Fishery, Soil and water conservation, Poultry, dairy Farming, Agriculture Marketing, Milk-fed financial institute and social forestry. Despite all other options, dairy farming is the best choice of the farmers as subsidiary occupation.

India's agri-exports face certain constraints that arise from conflicting domestic policies relating to production, storage, distribution, food security, pricing concerns etc. Unwillingness to decide on basic minimum quantities for export makes Indian supply sources unreliable. Higher domestic prices in comparison to international prices of products of bulk exports like sugar, wheat, rice etc. make our exports commercially less competitive. Market intelligence and creating awareness in international market about quality of products need to be strengthened to boost agricultural exports.

Statement of the Problem:

India is a leading exporter of many products. Export and import in India develops day by day. In this case export of agri and allied products which plays an important role in the development of economy of our country. There is the problem of agricultural industry were had an issues in product scarcity as well as following reasons: 1. there had a problem of labor scarcity for the production of agricultural goods. 2. Finding Buyers of agricultural products is not an easy task. 3. There occurs a major issue for transportation of products from one place to another. 4. Major thing was pricing; the products of agriculture won't get correct pricing for it. 5. Due to natural disaster there occurs major damage of agricultural products. 6. Sometimes there occurs theft and fraudulent activities. 7. Not having a clear idea about government schemes then there occurs losses. 8. Demands of the people cannot be satisfied due to lack of agricultural land usage. 9. Lack of implementing automated technologies for agri purpose. 10. Lack of warehouses for storage of agricultural products.

Objectives:

The research aims at entering the knowledge understanding role of export performance of agri and allied products. The following objective of the study.

- To assess the country wise performance of agri and allied products from India
- To analyse the theory of agri and allied products from India.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the project is involved the export performance of agri and allied products in Indian. The export performance of Indian agricultural and its allied products is affected by the high demand. The study also

gives growth rate and trend percentage of the export of agricultural goods year wise and also country wise. The study provides suggestion to the agri and allied products exporting industries to improve their performance.

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data:

The secondary data is collected to supplement the primary data. The annual reports of sample units, publication of agri and allied products in the website of ministry of commerce and industries, bulletins working and occasional papers of export import data bank were used as important sources of secondary data for the study.

Limitations of the Study:

- The analysis made only by considering 15 agri and allied products and 15 major countries.
- Time constraint is one of the limitations.

Period of Study:

The research data had done for 13 financial years, from the period of 2009-2022.

Review of Literature:

A study by Sarath Chandran (2010) used the Trade Intensity Index (TII) and RCA Index to see the trade complementarities and similarities between India and ASEAN countries. His study revealed that complementarities are available for both trading partners to enhance trade cooperation in some sectors and products. This study showed that India has advantages in exporting of food grains to small and less-developing ASEAN countries and importing edible oils and other agriculture products from other ASEAN countries. India enjoys comparative advantages in minerals, chemicals, iron and steel, gems and jewellery etc., while ASEAN countries have comparative advantage in electrical and electronic components that India can import. In brief, with the spread of regionalization all over the globe, the emerging economies warrant greater cooperation from India and vice-versa.

A study by Batra and Khan (2005) assessed the RCA index at the 2 as well as 6-digit level of HS classification to compare the comparative advantage of India and China. The study mainly focused on the changes in the structure of comparative advantage in the latter period (2002-2003). The authors also examined the comparative advantage of the two countries according to factor intensity using the SITC. The study does not find any structural changes in the comparative advantage of both the countries, except for some manufacturing sectors.

Burange and Chaddha (2008) evaluated the structure of comparative advantage in India and the change in the scene from 1996 to 2005. They used the data as per HS classification to compute the RCA index. The index is constructed at various levels of aggregation for exports and imports.

Export of Cashew from India:

Table 1

Year	Australia	Growth Rate	Bangladesh	Growth Rate	Canada	Growth Rate	China	Growth Rate	Germany	Growth Rate
2009	3,160.04		1,474.09		1,474.09		110.48		3,533.43	
2010	3298.86	4.39	2756.41	86.99	1688.29	14.53	1.53	-98.62	4156.97	17.65
2011	4553.34	38.03	2626.04	-4.73	3710.18	119.76	139.5	9017.65	9042.77	117.53
2012	1816.68	-60.1	1428.9	-45.59	2778.21	-25.12	94.89	-31.98	8679.01	-4.02
2013	1475.94	-18.76	1913.66	33.93	3477.75	25.18	3	-96.84	12150.14	39.99
2014	937.81	-36.46	1102.79	-42.37	3548.88	2.05	292.51	9650.33	21445.53	76.5
2015	973.26	3.78	965.78	-12.42	2283.17	-35.67	266.63	-8.85	14264.08	-33.49
2016	1926.59	97.95	2099.39	117.38	2487.83	8.96	6802.48	2451.28	15083.51	5.74
2017	2028.37	5.28	1264.81	-39.75	4739.73	90.52	855.48	-87.42	22983.76	52.38
2018	482.92	-76.19	187.57	-85.17	2729.29	-42.42	99.78	-88.34	10903.16	-52.56
2019	422.26	-12.56	200.13	6.7	1898.22	-30.45	132.6	32.89	15334.26	40.64
2020	773.43	83.16	0	-100	2073.45	9.23	0.31	-99.77	13931.22	-9.15
2021	567.66	-26.6	0.06	0	1366.81	-34.08	1	222.58	12037.88	-13.59
Total	22,417.16		16,019.63		34,255.90		8,800.19		1,63,545.72	
Average	1,724.40		1,232.28		2,635.07		676.94		12,580.44	

Values in Lakhs

(Source: EXIM data bank from ministry of commerce)

Trend Analysis of Cashew:

2022	-68		-166		2456		967		18236	
2023	-344		-550		2178		947		18236	
2024	-553		-742		1817		868		17791	
2025	-446		-891		1716		753		17607	
2026	-635		-1187		1477		568		16960	

Interpretation:

The above table shows the data of the product of cashew which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Australia. Australia had imported the cashew from India from the year of 2009 as 3160.04

lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 567.66 lakhs. This shows the export was decreased last year. The growth rate defines the value of 6 negative value and balance 6 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cashew were exported to Australia for the 5 years which shows the negative value. This shows the product demands were decreasing. The above table shows the data of the product of cashew which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Bangladesh. Bangladesh had imported the cashew from India from the year of 2009 as 1474.09 lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 0.06 lakhs. This shows the export was decreased last year. The growth rate defines the value of 7 negative value and balance 5 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cashew were exported to Bangladesh for the 5 years which shows the negative value. This shows the product demands were decreasing. The above table shows the data of the product of cashew which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Canada. Canada had imported the cashew from India from the year of 2009 as 110.48 lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 1lakh. This shows the export was decreased last year. The growth rate defines the value of 5 negative value and balance 7 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cashew were exported to Canada for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product has high demand. The above table shows the data of the product of cashew which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to China. China had imported the cashew from India from the year of 2009 as 3160.04 lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 567.66 lakhs. This shows the export was decreased last year. The growth rate defines the value of 7 negative value and balance 5 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cashew were exported to China for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product has high demand. The above table shows the data of the product of cashew which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Germany. Germany had imported the cashew from India from the year of 2009 as 3533.43 lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 12037.88 lakhs. This shows the export was increases last year. The growth rate defines the value of 5 negative value and balance 7 years shows the positive value. While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cashew were exported to Germany for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product were have a high demand.

Export of Cereals from India:

Table 2

Year	Australia	Growth Rate	Bangladesh	Growth Rate	Canada	Growth Rate	China	Growth Rate	Germany	Growth Rate
2009	3475.68		57371.61		6493.19		508.35		2030.09	
2010	5606.5	61.31	78585.06	36.98	10185.46	56.86	2563.66	404.31	2826.94	39.25
2011	11256.21	100.77	131371.61	67.17	18798.1	84.56	16914.4	559.77	10136.33	258.56
2012	15779.91	40.19	309642.7	135.7	18511.15	-1.53	8482.65	-49.85	9402.5	-7.24
2013	23064.1	46.16	563797.43	82.08	25570.96	38.14	10581.9	24.75	9712.07	3.29
2014	28042.22	21.58	520541.4	-7.67	32400.7	26.71	3239.17	-69.39	12722.07	30.99
2015	25590.57	-8.74	180918.02	-65.24	27472.35	-15.21	2167.68	-33.08	10956.59	-13.88
2016	24144.97	-5.65	41576.56	-77.02	23657.45	-13.89	866.58	-60.02	10963.42	0.06
2017	29331.92	21.48	562187.32	1252.17	33326.21	40.87	61.08	-92.95	10939.71	-0.22
2018	37702.75	28.54	205771.51	-63.4	41218.55	23.68	779.53	1176.24	11010.94	0.65
2019	43681.57	15.86	28767.67	-86.02	47715.27	15.76	725.45	-6.94	12836.49	16.58
2020	56312.81	28.92	736705.06	2460.88	59961.42	25.67	75904	10363.02	15072.39	17.42
2021	44101.17	-21.69	1672514.7	127.03	51617.92	-13.91	371897	389.96	12829.72	-14.88
Total	348090.38		5089750.7		396928.73		494692		131439.26	
Average	26776.183		391519.28		30532.979		38053.2		10110.712	

Values in Lakhs

(Source: Exim Data Bank from Ministry of Commerce)

Trend Analysis:

2022	53753		844490		57848		133582		15586	
2023	57572		919607		61629		155756		15716	
2024	61043		991642		65309		180029		15519	
2025	64670		1063646		69799		208638		16171	
2026	68368		1159000		73827		238155		16675	

Interpretation:

The above table shows the data of the product of cereals which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Australia. Australia had imported the cereals from India from the year of 2009 as 3475.68 lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 44101.17 lakhs. This shows the export has increases last year. The growth rate defines the value of 3 negative value and balance 9 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cereals were exported to Australia for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product has high demand. The above table shows the data of the product of cereals which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Bangladesh. Bangladesh had imported the cereals from India from the year of 2009 as 57371.61lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 1672514.7lakhs. This shows the export has increases last year. The growth rate defines the value of 5 negative value and balance 7 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cereals were exported to Bangladesh for

the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product has high demand. The above table shows the data of the product of cereals which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Canada. Canada had imported the cereals from India from the year of 2009 as 6493.19lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 51617.92lakhs. This shows the export has increases last year. The growth rate defines the value of 4 negative value and balance 8 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cereals were exported to Canada for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product has high demand. The above table shows the data of the product of cereals which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to China. China had imported the cereals from India from the year of 2009 as 508.35lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 371897lakhs. This shows the export has increases last year. The growth rate defines the value of 6 negative value and balance 6 years shows the positive value While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cereals were exported to China for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product demand has high demand. The above table shows the data of the product of cereals which was exported during the year of 2009-2022 from India to Germany. Germany had imported the cereals from India from the year of 2009 as 2030.09lakhs and in the year of 2022 as 12829.72lakhs. This shows the export has increases last year. The growth rate defines the value of 4 negative value and balance 8 years shows the positive value. While calculating the trend analysis for the product of cereals were exported to Germany for the 5 years which shows the positive value. This shows the product has high demand.

Findings:

- The above table shows the products of agri were known as cashew and cereals were exported to Australia were shown that the cereals export value has the positive results than the cashew had. Which means cereals has a chance for future trade.
- The above table shows the products of agri were known as cashew and cereals were exported to Bangladesh were shown that the cereals export value has the positive results than the cashew had. Which means cereals has a chance for future trade.
- The above table shows the products of agri were known as cashew and cereals were exported to Canada were shown that the cereals export value has the positive results than the cashew had. Which means cereals has a chance for future trade.
- The above table shows the products of agri were known as cashew and cereals were exported to China were shown that the cereals export value has the positive results than the cashew had. Which means cereals has a chance for future trade. Which means cereals has a chance for future trade.
- The above table shows the products of agri were known as cashew and cereals were exported to Germany were shown that the cashew as well as cereals had the positive results as equal. Which means cereals as well as cashew has a chance for future trade.
- Trend analysis of the country Australia shows the cashew export faces negative value and then the cereals show the positive results.
- Trend analysis of the country Bangladesh shows the cashew export faces negative value and then the cereals show the positive results.
- Trend analysis of the country Canada shows the cashew as well as cereals show the positive results.
- Trend analysis of the country China shows the cashew as well as cereals show the positive results.
- Trend analysis of the country Germany shows the cashew as well as cereals show the positive results.

Suggestions:

- Improve the cashew trade because it was lower than the trade of cereals. Basically, the three countries only have the positive results apart from the five countries for the products of cashew.
- The cereals had a good market in future that had a positive result in the trade of five countries and also had the huge buyers. It gives the good place for the India to make a stand in the foreign markets under the agri and allied products.
- The trend analysis shows the cereals will have a huge response in the foreign markets. Then the cashew has. Cereals has a high demand in foreign markets. While the India concentrate in cashew marketing in foreign markets means then the cashew will also reach higher like cereals.
- The data shows that the country called Germany which was the right place to sell this both products, because this product had the huge markets in the Germany.
- Cashew export promotion council wanted to analyse the current level of cashew. They wanted to motivate the exporters to make a good market of cashew as cereals had.

Conclusion:

The Policy aims at addressing a whole range of issues which could potentially propel India into the top bracket of agricultural exports. It has often been recognized that integration in the global value chain is one of the most certain methods of adopting the best agricultural practices along with attaining productivity gains and cost competitiveness. The objective of doubling the farmer's income will invariably require high levels of income as well as improving in the food value chain.

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